

Architecture of IEEE standard Low Voltage Direct Current (LVDC) Distribution System

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Acronyms and abbreviations

LVDC: Low Voltage Direct Current

LVAC: Low Voltage Alternating Current

IEEE: Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers

DERs: Distributed Energy Resources

BESS: Battery Energy Storage System

PV: Photo-Voltaic

WECS: Wind Energy Conversion System

PMSG: Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator

Abstract

The necessity for adequate and reliable electrical distribution systems that can maintain essential power supplies during disasters has been underscored by an increasing rate of natural catastrophic events and extreme weather situations. A Low Voltage Direct Current (LVDC) distribution system connected with Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) for disaster-resilient power delivery is modelled and analysed in this research. Compared with traditional LVAC distribution systems, the LVDC system is intended to increase power reliability, reduce conversion losses, improve operational efficiency, and enable the smooth integration of renewable energy sources. To evaluate system performance under various generation and load conditions, a comprehensive simulation model of an IEEE Standard prototype LVDC distribution system architecture is developed in MATLAB/Simulink. The recommended LVDC system successfully preserves voltage stability, enhances power quality, and guarantees dependable operation of critical loads during disaster-induced disruptions, according to simulation results. For emergency power distribution in disaster-prone areas, hospitals, shelters, and important infrastructure applications, the proposed model offers an efficient and resilient solution.

Keywords: LVDC, DERs, natural-disaster, LVAC, IEEE Std., resilience, renewable-energy integration, MATLAB/Simulink, critical loads.

I. INTRODUCTION

Low-Voltage Alternating Current (LVAC) distribution systems are extensively utilised in homes, businesses, and factory networks. LVAC systems are particularly appropriate for alternating current loads, including induction motors, fans, pumps, air conditioners, and standard domestic

appliances. The LVAC system is well-known, dependable, and accommodated by present electrical installations and protective systems. AC systems facilitate quicker fault interruption as the current generally reaches zero in each cycle. But LVAC systems exhibit poor efficiency for the latest DC loads. DC power can be generated directly by renewable energy sources like batteries and solar

III. THE PROPOSED MODEL

From the IEEE standards, The Block diagram of the proposed model of the prototype 48V LVDC Distribution System architecture is developed and shown in Figure 3[11]. The Proposed LVDC Distribution system mainly consists of

- i. DERs (Solar and wind energy conversion systems)
- ii. Utility grid.
- iii. DC feeders
- iv. DC loads
- v. Controllable Switches (CS)

Figure 3. Block diagram of the proposed model of the prototype 48V LVDC Distribution System architecture.

i. DERs:

(a) Photovoltaic (PV) Module

A module made of photovoltaic cells is used to convert solar energy into electrical energy [12]. Figure 5 below illustrates a PV-equivalent circuit using a single diode.

Figure 5 .PV equivalent circuit.

Model characteristic equations are developed for solar module voltage and current.

$$I = I_{pv} - I_s \left(e^{\left(\frac{V + IR_s}{\eta N_s V T} \right)} - 1 \right) - (V + IR_s) / R_p \text{ -----(1)}$$

The solar module's electrical settings are established in ideal circumstances, i.e., with a radiation level of 1000 W/m² and an ambient temperature of 25°C. Table 1 provides the solar panel model ND-1240Q2's specifications.

PV panel parameters	Rated value
V _{oc} Voltage at Open Circuit	37.5V
I _{sc} , current obtained at short circuit	8.61 A
Maximum Power P _{max}	240W
Voltage at Maximum Power	30.2V
Current at Maximum power	7.95 A

Table1.Datasheet of 240-watt PV module.

The supervisory control algorithm is designed to use commands in a Simulink "function block" to operate each load/distributor switch.

(b) Wind Energy Conversion System (WECS)

The Wind Energy Conversion System was regarded as an alternate DER in this investigation [13]. With PMSG (Permanent Magnet Synchronous Generator), a multi-pole and variable speed gearless design is seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Block diagram of a wind power production system using PMSG.

The WECS combines electrical and mechanical components. Usually, the power output of the wind turbine is

$$P = \frac{1}{2} \rho A v^3 \text{----- (2)}$$

Where;

P = Power available in wind (Watts)

ρ = Air density (kg/m³)

A = Swept area of turbine blades (m²)

v = Wind velocity (m/s)

Table 2 provides specifications for the 10kW power output synchronous machine with permanent magnet.

Parameters	Rated value
Base power	10KW
Base wind speed	12 m/s
Max power at base wind speed in p.u	0.85
Base rotational speed in p.u	1.2
Line-to-line rated voltage	48V
Rated power	10KW
Supply frequency	50HZ
D-axis inductance	0.41mH
Q-axis inductance	3.971mH
Stator leakage inductance	0.308mH
Stator resistance	2.90mΩ

Table 2. Block parameters of the wind turbine and the permanent magnet synchronous machine.

c. Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS)

Because they provide durable energy storage, backup power support, and power balancing under both regular and emergency operating situations, Battery Energy Storage Systems (BESS) are essential for LVDC distribution systems [14]. When renewable generation is insufficient or the utility grid collapses during a disaster, the BESS in an LVDC network stores excess energy produced by distributed energy resources (DERs) and provides power to DC loads.

ii. Utility grid:

A three-phase step-down transformer is used to shut down the three-phase 415 V AC supply from the grid to 48 V AC. A rectifier circuit is then used to convert the lowered AC voltage into DC. Three separate DC feeders are available to provide various DC loads separately from the rectified 48 V DC supply, which creates a common DC bus.

iii. DC feeders:

To serve various DC loads separately, the produced DC power is divided among three separate DC feeders that are coupled to a common DC bus. These DC feeders decrease power conversion losses, permit independent load control and protection, increase system dependability, and offer effective power distribution for typical applications like emergency loads [15].

415 V 3φ AC → Transformer → 48 V AC → Rectifier → 48 V DC → 3 DC Feeders

iv. DC loads:

Three types of DC loads are connected to each distributor or feeder. They are: Light load, Heater load and Motor load.

The Specifications of the heater load are:

Type of load: Heater Load (Resistive and Inductive)

Load capacity: 50 W to 250 W (in steps of 50 W)

Load Voltage: 48 V DC

The specifications of the light load are:

Type of load: Light load (Resistive load)

Load capacity: 50 W to 250 W (in steps of 50 W)

Load Voltage: 48 V DC

The specifications of the motor load are:

Type of load: Motor Load (Mostly Inductive)

Load capacity: 50W to 250W (variable according to mechanical loading)

Load Voltage: 48 V DC

v. Controllable Switches (CS)

Power electronic semiconductor devices known as controllable switches have ON and OFF states that may be managed by an external gate or control signal using a supervisory control method.

Distributed energy resources (DERs), including solar PV, wind energy systems, and battery storage, are automatically connected to the LVDC distribution system to deliver power to critical loads based on a supervisory control algorithm in the event of a disaster or utility grid failure. The logic control signal governs how the controllable switches (CS) function; logic "1" denotes an ON and connected switch, while logic "0" denotes an OFF and disconnected switch [16].

IV. RESULTS and DISCUSSIONS

Figure 6 illustrates the MATLAB/Simulink design of the IEEE Recommended Practice 48V prototype LVDC distribution system

architecture.

Figure 6. MATLAB/SIMULINK model of 48V prototype LVDC Distribution System architecture.

The DERs supply the electrical energy in batteries when the utility grid is turned ON, meaning that all three feeds and nine loads consume the power from the main utility grid. Figure 7 illustrates that all three feeders (F1, F2, and F3) have "1" or ON switching pulses.

Figure 7. The feeders F1, F2 and F3 are ON.

The proposed LVDC distribution system's performance under normal and grid failure cases. The system runs in AC mode with balanced three-phase voltage and current waveforms before the grid outage (0–0.08 s). During the "Grid OFF" situation at 0.08 seconds, the battery energy storage system (BESS) and distributed energy resources (DERs) continue to deliver power to the DC feeders that are given priority while maintaining a uniform 48 V DC bus voltage. While the power waveforms show continuous power supply to critical loads with little variation, the current waveforms demonstrate that the DC feeder currents stay constant based on load priority. These findings show how well the recommended LVDC system works to deliver a dependable, effective, and continuous power supply in the event of a utility grid

outage shown in the figure 8

Figure 8. The voltage, current and power waveforms of the LVDC Distribution system.

The LVDC system demonstrates better voltage regulation, higher efficiency, and reduced power losses compared to the conventional LVAC system is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Comparison between LVAC and Proposed LVDC Distribution Architecture.

The power comparison also indicates that the LVDC system efficiently supplies power to prioritised feeders during grid failure conditions using distributed energy resources (DERs).

V. CONCLUSION

When compared to the traditional LVAC system, the MATLAB/Simulink modelling and simulation of the recommended LVDC distribution system shows that the LVDC architecture offers superior efficiency, better voltage control, lower power losses, and increased reliability for contemporary DC loads. In the proposed system, electricity is distributed across many DC feeders to supply priority loads after the utility grid supply is

transformed from 415 V three-phase AC to 48 V DC using a transformer and rectifier setup. Through intelligent priority-based regulation employing programmable switches, the DERs and Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) reliably ensure a continuous power supply to critical loads under utility grid failure situations brought on by natural catastrophes.

In comparison to the traditional LVAC system, the simulation waveforms and comparison charts verify that the LVDC system maintains steady DC bus voltage, effective feeder current distribution, and continuous power supply with reduced transmission losses. As a result, the proposed LVDC distribution system architecture is an effective and appropriate option for future robust power distribution networks, emergency power applications, and the integration of renewable energy.

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The authors affirm that the work described in this publication was not influenced by any known conflicting financial interests or Personal ties.

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